

Possible relationships between single nucleotide polymorphisms and expression of human HBA1, HBA2, HBB and HBD genes

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Functional assessment of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) is one of the effective approaches in evolutionary biology, mapping of genes and loci of monogenic and complex diseases, and determination of regulatory elements of genomes. In particular, in the case of beta-globin genes, SNPs can lead to thalassemia of varying severity. To date, more than 324 million SNPs and short (no longer than 50 bp) insertions/deletions identified in the human genome have been collected in dbSNP resources (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp/>). The article presents the results of studies on the influence of single nucleotide polymorphisms on gene expression in humans using two families (alpha and beta) of globin genes, HBA1 and HBA2, HBB and HBD. An analysis of 5454 (1245, 1181, 1777, and 1251) known SNPs and indels in these genes showed that 310 (24, 55, 221, and 10) mutations may be associated with known pathologies and 183 (28, 22, 132, and 1) mutations are "ineffective" mutations (i.e., without symptoms), and the remaining 4961 (~91%) variations are functionally and clinically insignificant. Among SNPs of pathological effect, 262, 25, and 23 variations are localized, respectively, in DNA coding sequences, 5'-untranslated regions (including promoters and potential transcription factor binding sites), and introns. These results are consistent with the known evidence that the genetic causes of some clinical complications are mutations in non-coding regions of genes.

Keywords: HBA1, HBA2, HBB, HBD, single nucleotide polymorphism, promoter, transcription factor binding site

INTRODUCTION

Only a few percent of the human genome encodes proteins and known RNA molecules. At the same time, at least 60% of the human genome is transcribed, and at least 20% of these transcripts carry some functional load (Davis et al., 2018; <https://www.encodeproject.org/>). Therefore, we must also try to understand the function of extragenic regions (near genes and intergenic spacers) of the human genome, including transcribed DNA sequences of unknown function.

One of the simple but effective approaches in this direction is the functional assessment of a rapidly growing number of genetic polymorphisms (GPs), which are defined as a Mendelian trait that occurs in a population in two variants with a frequency of at least 1% for each (Marchini et al., 2007). GPs can be quantitative and qualitative. Quantitative GPs make up more than 50% of the entire genome. They include elements such as micro-

and mini-satellite DNAs forming Short Tandem Repeats (*STR*), retrotransposons, longer repeats with a variable internal structure in nucleotide composition (Shastry, 2009; Alkan, Coe and Eichler, 2011; Zarrei et al., 2015; Lauer and Gresham, 2019). Qualitative GPs are represented by a Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (*SNP*). SNPs are the most common type of genome variability (Wang, Luhm and Lei, 2007; Mielczarek and Szyda, 2016). It is difficult to overestimate the role of SNPs, which can be used for evolutionary studies, mapping of genes and loci of monogenic and complex diseases. In the case of beta-globin genes, this leads to the emergence of beta-thalassemia, a monogenic thalassemia disease of varying severity. The first SNPs were found in the 3' region of the human beta-globin gene (Green and King, 1989). To date, more than 324 million SNPs and short (≤ 50 bp) insertions/deletions (indel) identified in the human genome have been collected in the dbSNP resources (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp/>). On average,

there is one SNP per 300 nucleotides (de Vries et al., 2017).

Last 15 years, the study of the relationships of such variations with certain functions, genetic diseases and clinical symptoms has become widespread, and a number of important and interesting results have been obtained. Such studies of the association can be performed on individual genes, families of genes, or on the genome as a whole. About 50% of SNPs were estimated to occur in non-coding regions and out of them, about 25% lead to missense mutations, and the remaining ~25% lead to silent mutations (Sherry et al, 2001). Some of the SNPs are involved in the formation of quantitative traits and phenotype. Such SNPs affect transcription and mRNA splicing. Functional SNPs can also affect protein function, structure, and stability (Ramirez-Bello et al., 2013).

In recent years, the genome-wide association study (GWAS) method has been widely used (Clark et al., 2005). This method allows identifying the risks of various diseases and requires the analysis of a large number of sick and healthy (control) people. According to the results of GWAS, SNPs located in exons represent a minority. Although GWAS for some allelic variants may show an association with the disease, they may not actually be related to the disease. This can be explained by their linkage with functionally significant loci. Each disease-associated polymorphism marks a rather extended area, within which functionally significant SNPs are located.

Changes in gene expression are associated with many diseases. Most SNPs play a regulatory role (Chorley et al., 2008). Thus, defects in the regions of mRNA processing regulation lead not only to a quantitative insufficiency of gene expression but also to the formation of abnormal mRNAs that do not have functional activity (Ceci et al., 2006; Pastinen et al., 2000). SNPs can also cause mutational changes in the ATG start codon (Negre et al., 2016) or terminator codons. Approximately 40 polymorphisms of TATA promoters associated with certain human diseases have been found (Savinkova et al., 2009). Besides, there are known cases of converting the TATA box into another site. Thus, in the presence of SNP -33 T>C, the TATA box is converted into the transcription factor (TF) GATA -1 and represses the DARC gene, which increases resistance to malaria in most indigenous people of West Africa (Tournamille et al., 1995). In another case, SNP -26 G>C and -20 T>A polymorphisms lead to hemophilia B-Leiden (Reijnen et al., 1992)

It is known that the first and, in most cases, the decisive step in the expression of genetic information (including genes) is transcription. Most

regulatory events occur at the transcriptional level and are mediated by the interaction of TFs with regulatory regions of DNA, which are concentrated in the promoter region near the Transcription Start Site (TSS). The key “players” in transcription control are transcription factor binding sites (TFBSs). TFBSs are usually short regions of DNA of 5-15 nucleotides, and mutations occurring in them significantly affect their activity (Butler and Kadonaga, 2002; Hahn, 2004; Schier and Taatjes, 2020; Smale and Kadonaga, 2003; Solovyev, Shahmuradov and Salamov 2010; Juven-Gershon et al., 2008; Woychik and Hampsey, 2002). Many SNPs are localized in promoter areas. Several forms of β -thalassemia have been described with mutational changes in the promoter element, the Goldberg-Hogness box (CATAAA) which is localized in the 5'-flanking region of the β -globin gene. A single nucleotide substitution in the CATAAA element was found in the Chinese form (CATAgA; Davies et al., 2003) and Kurdish form (CATAcA; Morozova and Marra, 2008) of β -thalassemia.

Moreover, for a long time, promoters were considered unidirectional, i.e., they initiate the transcription of only one DNA strand (Bagchi and Iyer, 2016). However, in the last decade, many bidirectional promoters (BDPs) have been found in the genomes of humans and other eukaryotes. In eukaryotic genomes, thousands of pairs of genes are located on opposite strands of DNA (Adachi and Lieber 2002; Kaplan, 2016; Trinklein et al., 2004; Wei et al., 2011; Yang et al., 2007). Such genes are transcribed by BDPs (if they are several hundred nucleotides apart) or by two adjacent divergent promoters (if they are at a longer distance from each other).

This research was devoted to studying the possible effect of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) on the expression of human alpha- and beta-globin genes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DNA sequences of the human HBA1, HBA2, HBB, and HBD genes encoding alpha- and beta-globin polypeptides, as well as their 5'- and 3'- untranslated regions (5'-UTR, 3'-UTR), were taken from the human genome annotation (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/projects/genome/guide/human/index.shtml#download>; GRCh38). The SNP/indel data were taken from the dbSNP resources (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp/>).

To compare nucleotide and protein sequences, **BLAST** (Altschul et al., 1997) and **BLAN** (Shahmuradov, unpublished) tools were used. A

search for unidirectional and bidirectional promoters (UDP and BDP, respectively) for the RNA Polymerase II (Pol II) were carried out using the **TSShm** and **BDPGfinder** computer programs (Shahmuradov, unpublished), respectively. TSShm searches for 3 classes of Pol II promoters (CpG, non-CpG/TATA, and non-CpG/non-TATA) on both strands of a given query DNA sequence. Based on TSShm results, the BDPGfinder computer program identifies adjacent pairs of genes located at certain distances in opposite DNA chains. Search for promoters and TFBS was performed in the 5'-region of each gene ([-1000: +100], +1 corresponds to the annotated gene start). Here and further, a bidirectional promoter means a region of DNA that includes two opposite TSS at a distance of no more than 300 bp. The condition “ ≤ 300 bp” is connected with the fact that the length of the proximal promoter is considered to be 200-300 bp.

The search for statistically non-random motifs of known human TFBSs was conducted using the **Nsite** program (Shahmuradov and Solovyev, 2015). The human TFBS set was created on the basis of TFBSs collected in databases (1) ooTFD (Ghosh, 2000) and (2) RegsiteAN Company Softberry, USA (unpublished), and contained 652 known TFBSs. The creation of gene-specific sets of SNP/indel based on dbSNP data and their general statistical

analysis were carried out using the computer program **getnpp** (Shahmuradov, unpublished). TFBSs, identified in the promoter regions of genes, were compared with the positions of SNP/indel using the computer program **comp_TFBS_SNP** (Shahmuradov, unpublished).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distribution and effect of known SNPs and indels in genes HBA1, HBA2, HBB, and HBD.

The HBA1 and HBA2, HBB and HBD genes encode the main polypeptides of alpha- and beta-globins in an adult. Analysis of 5454 (respectively 1245, 1181, 1777, and 1251) known SNPs and indels in these genes (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp/>) showed that 310 (24, 55, 221, and 10) mutations can be associated with known pathologies and 183 (28, 22, 132, and 1) mutations are asymptomatic, and the remaining 4961 (~91%) variations are seemingly insignificant. Among SNPs of pathological effect, 262, 25, and 23 variations are localized, respectively, in CDS, 5'-UTR, and introns (Table 1).

Table 1. General statistics on localization and effect of known SNPs and indels in the human HBA1, HBA2, HBB, and HBD genes

Quantity and localization SNP/indel	Genes			
	HBA1	HBA2	HBB	HBD
Total (SNP/indel)	1245 (1129/116)	1181 (1050/131)	1777 (1461/316)	1251 (1142/109)
SNP with pathological effect	24	55	221	10
SNP without pathological effect,	28	22	132	1
SNP with unknown effect	1193	1104	1424	1240
In DNA coding sequences:				
Total:	299	312	540	225
with pathological effect,	23	39	158	5
without pathological effect,	14	10	39	1
with unknown effect	262	263	343	219
5'-UTR:				
Total:	612	565	625	494
with pathological effect,	0	1	16	3
without pathological effect,	3	0	4	0
with unknown effect	609	564	605	491
3'-UTR:				
Total:	144	113	131	153
with pathological effect,	0	0	1	1
without pathological effect,	5	2	9	0
with unknown effect	139	111	121	152
In introns:				
Total:	108	103	385	303
with pathological effect,	0	0	22	1
without pathological effect,	4	7	76	0
with unknown effect	104	96	287	302
In near regions:				
Total:	82	88	96	76
with pathological effect,	1	15	24	0
without pathological effect,	2	3	4	0
with unknown effect	79	70	68	76

Promoter analysis of the HBA1, HBA2, HBB, and HBD genes

Using the TSShm program, a search for possible TSSs in the promoter region [-1000: +100] of each of the HBA1, HBA2, HBB, and HBD genes was carried

out. Two possible BDPs for the HBA1 and HBA2 genes and one putative UDP for each of the HBB and HBD genes were identified. Applying the Nsite tool in the promoter region of analyzed genes, statistically nonrandom motifs of known TFBSs were found (Fig. 1, 2, 3 and 4; Table 2, 3, 4 and 5).

1	GTCACCTTGA	ATGCCTCGTC	CACACCTCCA	GACTTCCTCA	GGGCCTGTGA
51	TGAGGTCTGC	ACCTCTGTGT	GTACTTGTGT	GATGGTTAGA	GGACTGCCTA
101	CCTCCCAGAG	GAGGTTGAAT	GCTCCAGCCG	GTTCCAGCTA	TTGCTTTGTT
151	TACCTGTTTA	ACCAGTATTT	ACCTAGCAAG	TCTT CCATCA	GATAGC ATTT
201	GGAGAGCTGG	GGGTGTC ACA	GTGAACC ACG	ACCTCTAGGC	CAGTGGGAGA
251	GTCAGTCACA	CAAAC TGTGA	GTCCATGACT	TGGGGCTTAG	CCAGCACCCA
301	CCACCCACG	CGCCACCCA	CAACCCCGG	TAGAGGAGTC	TGAATCTGGA
351	GCCGCCCCA	G CCAGCCCC	GTGCTTTTTG	CGTCCTGGTG	TTTATTCCTT
401	CCCGGT GCCT	GTCA CTCAAG	CACACTAGTG	ACTATCGCCA	GAGGGAAAGG
451	GAGCTGCAGG	AAGCGAGGCT	GGAG AGCAGG	AGGGGCT CTG	CGCAGAAATT
501	CTTTTGAGTT	CCTATGGGCC	AGGGCGTCCG	GGTGCGCGCA	TTCCTCTCCG
551	CCCAGGATT	GGCGAAGCC	TCCCGGCTCG	CACTCGCTCG	CCCGTGTGTT
601	CCCCGATCCC	GCTGGAGTCG	ATGCGCGTCC	AGCGCGTGCC	AGGCCG GGGC
651	GGGG GTGCGG	GCTGACTTTC	TCCCTCGCTA	GGGACGCTCC	GGCGCCCGAA
701	AGGAAAGGGT	GCGCTGCGC	TCCGGGGTGC	ACGAGCCGAC	AGCGCCCGAC
751	CCCAACGGGC	CGGCCCCGCC	AGCGCCGCTA	CCGCCCTGCC	CCCGGGCGAG
801	CGGGATGGGC	GGGAGTGGAG	TGGCGGGTGG	AGGGTGGAGA	CGTCCTGGCC
851	CCCGCCCCGC	GTGCACCCCC	AGGGGAGGCC	GAGCCCGCCG	CCCGGCCCCG
901	CGCAGGCCCC	GCCCGGGACT	CCCCTGCGGT	CCAGGCCGCG	CCC CGGGCTC
951	CGCGCCAGCC	AATGA GCGCC	GCCCGGCCGG	GCGTGCCCCC	GCGCCCCAAG
1001	CATAA ACCCT	GCGCGCTCG	CGGCCCGGCA	CTCTTCTGGT	CCCCACAGAC
1051	TCAGAGAGAA	CCCACCATGG	TGCTGTCTCC	TGCCGACAAG	ACCAACGTCA

Fig. 1. The nucleotide sequence of the [-1000: +100] region of the human HBA1 gene and some statistically non-random TFBS motifs including known SNPs (in bold and underlined). ①: RSA00393: GATA-3; ②: RSA00545: c-Myb BS; ③: RSA00838: SP1 BS; ④: RSA00482: SP1 BS; ⑤: RSA00227: Sp2/Sp3 BS; ⑥: ooTFD/S03405: CTF BS (alpha globin); ⑦: RSA01330: NF-Y BS (element CCAAT).

Here and below, position 1001 corresponds to the annotated gene start. Two potential BDPs (TSS pairs: 897←→978 and 538←→596) are highlighted in green. Here and below, the TFBS identifiers (IDs) proposed in the ooTFD and RegsiteAN databases are used. For more information see Table 2.

```

1   GATGCACCCA CTGGCACTCC TGCACCTCCC ACCCTCCCCC TCGCCAAGTC
51  CACCCCTTCC TTCCTCACCC CACATCCCCT CACCTACATT CTGCAACCAC
101 AGGGGCCTTC TCTCCCCTGT CCTTTCCCTA CCCAGAGCCA AGTTTGTTTA
151 TCTGTTTACA ACCAGTATTT ACCTAGCAAG TCTTCCATCA GATAGCATTT
201 GGAGAGCTGG GGGTGTCACA GTGAACCACG ACCTCTAGGC CAGTGGGAGA
251 GTCAGTCACA CAAACTGTGA GTCCATGACT TGGGGCTTAG CCAGCACCCA
301 CCACCCCG CGCCACCCCA CAACCCCGGG TAGAGGAGTC TGAATCTGGA
351 GCCGCCCCCA GCCCAGCCCC GTGCTTTTTG CGTCCTGGTG TTTGTTCCCTT
401 CCCGGTGCC TCACTCAAG CACTACTAGTG ACTATCGCCA GAGGGAAAGG
451 GAGCTGCAGG AAGCGAGGCT GGAGAGCAGG AGGGGCTCTG CGCAGAAATT
501 CTTTTGAGTT CCTATGGGCC AGGGCGTCCG GGTGCGCGCA TTCCTCTCCG
551 CCCCAGGATT GGGCGAAGCC CTCCGGCTCG CACTCGCTCG CCCGTGTGTT
601 CCCCGATCCC GCTGGAGTCG ATGCGCGTCC AGCGCGTGCC AGGCCGGGGC
651 GGGGGTGCGG GCTGACTTTC TCCCTCGCTA GGGACGCTCC GCGCCCCGAA
701 AGGAAAGGGT GGCCTGCGC TCCGGGGTGC ACGAGCCGAC AGCGCCCGAC
751 CCCAACGGGC CGGCCCCGCC AGCGCCGCTA CCGCCCTGCC CCCGGGCGAG
801 CGGGATGGGC GGGAGTGGAG TGGCGGGTGG AGGGTGGAGA CGTCCTGGCC
851 CCCGCCCCGC GTGCACCCCC AGGGGAGGCC GAGCCCGCCG CCCGGCCCCG
901 CGCAGGCCCC GCCCGGGACT CCCCTGCGGT CCAGGCCGCG CCCCGGGCTC
951 CGCGCCAGCC AATGAGCGCC GCCCGGCCGG GCGTGCCCCC GCGCCCCAAG
1001 CATAAACCTT GCGCGCTCG CGGGCCGGCA CTCTTCTGGT CCCACAGAC
1051 TCAGAGAGAA CCCACCATGG TGCTGTCTCC TGCCGACAAG ACCAACGTCA

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Annotations in the sequence:

- ①: **CCATCA** (underlined)
- ②: **ACA** (underlined)
- ③: **GTGAACC** (underlined)
- ④: **CG** (underlined)
- ⑤: **AGCAGG** (underlined)
- ⑥: **GGGG** (underlined)
- ⑦: **GCC** (underlined)

Two possible BDPs (TSS pairs) are highlighted in green:

- 897 ← → 978
- 538 ← → 596

Fig. 2. The nucleotide sequence of the [-1000:+100] region of the human HBA2 gene and some statistically non-random TFBS motifs including known SNPs (in bold and underlined). ①: RSA00393:: GATA-3 BS; ②: RSA00545:: c-Myb BS ③: RSA00889:: BF: NF-E2/AP1 BS ;④: RSA00382:: Sp1 BS; ⑤: RSA00482:: SP1 BS; ⑥: RSA00227:: Sp2/Sp3 BS ; ⑦: RSA00526:: NF-Y BS (CCAAT). Two possible BDPs (TSS pairs: 897 ← → 978 and 538 ← → 596) are highlighted in green. For more information see Table 3.

```

1   GGAACTTGAA TCAAGGAAAT GATTTTAAAA CGCAGTATTC TTAGTGGACT
51  AGAGGAAAAA AATAATCTGA GCCAAGTAGA AGACCTTTTC CCCTCCTACC
101 CCTACTTTCT AAGTCACAGA GGCTTTTTGT TCCCCCAGAC ACTCTTGCAG
151 ATTAGTCCAG GCAGAAACAG TTAGATGTCC CCAGTTAACC TCCTATTTGA
201 CACCACTGAT TACCCCATG ATAGTCACAC TTTGGGTTGT AAGTGACTTT
251 TTATTTATTT GTATTTTGA CTGCATTAAG AGGTCTCTAG TTTTTTATCT
301 CTTGTTTCCC AAAACCTAAT AAGTAACTAA TGCACAGAGC ACATTGATTT
                                     CCT ←
351 GTATTTATTC TATTTT TAGA CATAATTTAT TAGCATGCAT GAGCAAATTA
-----
401 AGAAAAACAA CAACAAATGA ATGCATATAT ATGTATATGT ATGTGTGTAT
-----
451 ATATACACAC ATATATATAT ATATTTTTTC TTTTCTTACC AGAAGGTTTT
      → CCT
      ①
501 AATCCAAATA AGGAGAAGAT ATGCTTAGAA CCGAGGTAGA GTTTTTCATCC
551 ATTCTGTCCT GTAAGTATTT TGCATATTCT GGAGACGCAG GAAGAGATCC
601 ATCTACATAT CCCAAAGCTG AATTATGGTA GACAAAAC TCCTACTTTT
651 AGTGCATCAA CTTCTTATTT GTGTAATAAG AAAATTGGGA AAACGATCCT
701 CAATATGCTT ACCAAGCTGT GATTCCAAAT ATTACGTAAA TACACTTGCA
751 AAGGAGGATG TTTT TAGTAG CAATTTGTAC TGATGGTATG GGGCCAAGAG
      ③          ④
801 ATATATCTTA GAGGGAGGGC TGAGGGTTTG AAGTCCAAC CCTAAGCCAG
851 TGCCAGAAGA GCCAAGGACA GGTACGGCTG TCATCACTTA GACCTCACCC
901 TGTGGAGCCA CACCCTAGGG TTGGCCAATC TACTCCCAGG AGCAGGGAGG
      ⑤          ⑥          ⑦
951 GCAGGAGCCA GGGCTGGGCA TAAAAGTCAG GGCAGAGCCA TCTATTGCTT
1001 ACATTTGCTT CTGACACAAC TGTGTTCACT AGCAACCTCA AACAGACACC
1051 ATGGTGCATC TGA CTCTGA GGAGAAGTCT GCCGTTACTG CCCTGTGGGG

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Fig. 3. The nucleotide sequence of the [-1000: +100] region of the human HBB gene and some statistically non-random TFBS motifs including known SNPs (in bold and underlined). ①: ooTFD/S03873: BP1 BS; ②: RSA00578: CBF BS (CArG); ③: RSA00039: Sp BS; ④: RSA01085: E2F BS; ⑤: RSA01009: Ets1 BS; ⑥: RSA00735: SP1 BS; ⑦: RSA01233: HNF-4/RXRalpha, RXRalpha/RARalpha, RXRalpha/T3Rbeta BS. The TSS pair of the potential BDP is highlighted in green: 346←→461. For more information see Table 4.

Fig. 4. The nucleotide sequence of the [-1000: +100] region of the human HBD gene and some statistically non-random TFBS motifs including known SNPs (in bold and underlined). ①: RSA00377: Elk-1 BS; ②: RSA00377: Elk-1 BS; ③: RSA01009: Ets1 BS; ④: RSA01164: AP-1 BS; ⑤: RSA00052: IRF-1 BS; ⑥: RSA00971: C/EBP BS; ⑦: RSA01301: Sp1 BS; ⑧: RSA01164: AP-1 BS. The TSS pair of the potential BDP is highlighted in green: 603↔667. For more information see Table 5.

Table 2. Statistically non-random TFBS motifs found in the [-1000: +100] region of the HBA1 gene and SNP/indel variations in these motifs

№	TFBS ID	TF	TFBS motif ¹	Known SNPs in TFBS motifs ²
1	RSA00022	MyoD Myf4/Myf6	407- GCCTGTCA-414	ID: rs562871086 SNP ⁴¹³ : C>T
2	RSA00227	Sp2 Sp3	646- GGGGCGGGG-654	ID: rs1196721461 SNP ⁶⁴⁷ : G>A
3	RSA00326	PU.1 GABPalpha	548- GAGAGGAA-541	ID: rs1198006864 SNP ⁵⁴¹ : T>C
4	RSA00382	Sp1	321- GtGGGGTGGCGCG-309	ID: rs796845372 SNP ³¹¹ : C>T
5	RSA00393	Sp1	196- gCTATCTGATgG-185	ID: rs1596572372 SNP ¹⁹⁶ : C>T
6	RSA00482	Sp1	475-AGcAGGAGGGGcT-487	ID:rs887790592 SNP ⁴⁸⁶ :C>A

Table 2 continued

7	RSA00526	NF-Y	967-GCTcATTGGC-958	ID:rs1191288315 SNP ⁹⁶² :A>G
8	RSA00545	c-Myb	218- ACaGTGAACC-227	ID:rs1254448475 SNP ²²¹ :G>A
9	RSA00581	NF-MATp35	504-AAAGAAAtTTC-495	ID:rs1004854583 SNP ⁴⁹⁵ :G>A
10	RSA00611	SP1	646-GGGGCGGGG-654	ID:rs1196721461 SNP ⁶⁴⁷ :G>A
11	RSA00838	SP1	362-CCCAGCCCC-370	ID:rs996202193 SNP ³⁶⁷ :C>T
12	RSA00842	Sp1	871-AGGgGAGGCCG-881	ID:rs1239044656 SNP ⁸⁷⁸ :G>A
13	RSA00889	NF-E2/AP1	273-CCATGACTtgGgGCT-287	ID:rs1355388924 SNP ²⁷⁹ :C>T
14	RSA00944	NF-IL6	263-TTGTGTgAC-255	ID:rs553770674 SNP ²⁵⁵ :G>A
15	RSA00948	SP1	935-GCCGCGCCCC-944	ID:rs979573171 SNP ⁹⁴³ :C>G
16	RSA01162	Sp1	554-GGGGCGGAG-546	ID:rs1190854966 SNP ⁵⁵² :C>T
17	RSA01305	Pdx1	442-AGGGAAAgGG-451	ID:rs1214175453 SNP ⁴⁵⁰ :->T ³
18	RSA01330	NF-Y	965-TCATTGG-959	ID:rs1191288315 SNP ⁹⁶² :A>G
19	RSA01472	AP-1	258-TGACTGA-252	ID:rs553770674 SNP ²⁵⁵ :G>A
20	ooTFD/S0340 5	CTF	944-CGGGCTCCGCGCCAGCCAATGAGCGCCGCC-973	ID:rs925033734 SNP ⁹⁵⁴ :G>T
21	ooTFD/ S03430	Sp1	327-GGGgttGTGGGGTGGCGC - 310	ID:rs796845372 SNP ³¹¹ :C>T

³Compared to the known TFBS, matching and non-matching nucleotides are indicated, respectively, by capital and small letters. ⁴SNP identifier corresponds to the dbSNP (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp/>). ⁵Insertion.

Table 3. Statistically non-random TFBS motifs found in the [-1000: +100] region of the HBA2 gene and SNP/indel variations in these motifs

Nº	TFBS ID	TF	TFBS motif	Known SNPs in TFBS motifs
1	RSA00022	MyoD; Myf4/Myf6	407- GCCTGTCA- 414	ID: rs1209931576 SNP ⁴¹³ : C>T
2	RSA00227	Sp2	646 -GGGGCGGGG -654	ID: rs1322384220 SNP ⁶⁴⁹ : G>A
3	RSA00326	PU.1	548 - GAGAGGAA -541	ID: rs1596569080 SNP ⁵⁴⁵ : T>A,C
4	RSA00382	GABPalph Sp1	321 -GtGGGGTGGCGCG -309	ID: rs576677996 SNP ³¹¹ : C>T
5	RSA00393	GATA-3	196 - gCTATCTGATgG -185	ID: rs552691844 SNP ¹⁹⁶ : C>T
6	RSA00394	GATA-3	153 - AGATAA -148	ID: rs947311073 SNP ¹⁵⁰ : A>T
7	RSA00482	Sp1	475 - AGcAGGAGGGGcT -487	ID: rs1407769241 SNP ⁴⁷⁷ : C>T
8	RSA00545	c-Myb	218 - ACaGTGAACC -227	ID: rs890237008 SNP ²²² : T>G
9	RSA00581	NF-MATp35	504 - AAAGAAAtTTC -495	ID: rs898886649 SNP ⁴⁹⁹ : T>C
10	RSA00611	SP1	646 - GGGGCGGGG - 654	ID: rs1322384220 SNP ⁶⁴⁹ : G>A
11	RSA00628	H1TF1	396 - AACAAACACcAg -385	ID: rs143196637 SNP ³⁹⁴ : G>A,T
12	RSA00889	NF-E2/AP1	273- CCATGACTtgGgGCT- 287	ID: rs1315956202 SNP ²⁷⁶ : T>G
13	RSA01305	Pdx1	442 - AGGGAAAgGG -451	ID: rs530196712 SNP ⁴⁴³ : G>A
14	RSA01472	AP-1	258 -TGACTGA - 252	ID: rs1226207898 SNP ²⁵⁴ : A>G

Table 4. Statistically non-random TFBS motifs found in the [-1000: +100] region of the HBB gene and SNP/indel variations in these motifs

Nº	TFBS ID	TF	TFBS motif	Known SNPs in TFBS motifs
1	RSA00039	Sp family	811 - GaGGGAGGG -819	ID: rs753344875 SNP ⁸¹¹ : C>T
2	RSA00374	PUF	813 - GGGaGGGCTG -822	ID: rs1021796402 SNP ⁸²² : C>T
3	RSA00578	CBF	504 - CCAAATAAGGa -514	ID: rs74049330 SNP ⁵¹⁰ : T>G
4	RSA00632	H4TF1	811 - GaGGGAGGG - 819	ID: rs753344875 SNP ⁸¹¹ : C>T
5	RSA00735	SP1	961- GGGCtGGGC - 969	ID: rs34500389 SNP ⁹⁶⁹ : G>A,T
6	RSA00838	SP1	968 - CCCAGCCCt - 960	ID: rs1160543272 SNP ⁹⁶⁸ : C>A,T
7	RSA00976	Sp1	968 - CCCAGCCCt -960	ID: rs1160543272 SNP ⁹⁶⁸ : C>A,T
8	RSA01009	Ets1	947 - GAGGGcAGGA -956	ID: rs281864524 SNP ⁹⁵¹ : C>T
9	RSA01085	E2F	813 -GGGagGGcTgAgGGTTTGAA -832	ID: rs117785782 SNP ⁸²⁸ : A>G
10	RSA01138	SP1	961 - GGGCtGGGC -969	ID: rs34500389 SNP ⁹⁶⁹ : G>A,T
11	RSA01273	Oct-4	386- ATGCTAAT - 379	ID: rs994847274 SNP ³⁸⁰ : A>G
12	RSA01286	MAZ/Sp1	584 - GaCGCaGGAAG - 594	ID: rs866544354 SNP ⁵⁸⁷ : C>T
13	RSA01474	NFAT	61 - tTTTTTCTCT -51	ID: rs1049469874 SNP ⁵⁹ : T>C

Table 5. Statistically non-random TFBS motifs found in the [-1000: +100] region of the HBD gene and SNP/indel variations in these motifs.

Nº	TFBS ID	TF	TFBS motif	Known SNPs in TFBS motifs
1	RSA00052	IRF-1	894 - AGTTTCAtTTTt - 883	ID:rs540457381 SNP ⁸⁹² : T>C
2	RSA00326	PU.1; GABPalph	45 - GAGAGGAA - 38	ID :rs531552954 SNP ⁴³ : G>T
3	RSA00375	BF: Ets-1/Pu.1	661 - agGAGGAAGC - 670	ID: rs1048024251 SNP ⁶⁶⁶ : C>A
4	RSA00377	Elk-1	669 - CtTCCTcCTTC -659	ID :rs887595179 SNP ⁶⁶⁰ : T>C
5	RSA00387	24 kDa protein	1027 - GAAGGTT -1033	ID: rs544924585 SNP ¹⁰³⁰ : C>T
6	RSA00474	NF-kappaB	959 -GGGTTTC -965	ID: rs80138317 SNP ⁹⁵⁹ : C>T
7	RSA00482	Sp1	178 - AGGAaGAGGGGaA -166	ID: rs560160001 SNP ¹⁷³ : G>T
8	RSA00648	NF-E2	972 - TGACTCAG -965	ID:rs1564879538 SNP ⁹⁶⁶ : A>G
9	RSA00789	SP1; SP3	1100 - CCCTgCTCCa -1091	ID:rs34796568 SNP ¹⁰⁹¹ : A>G
10	RSA00881	C/EBP alpha	444 -CTTTAGTCATA - 454	ID: rs893713201 SNP ⁴⁵¹ : G>T
11	RSA00971	C/EBP	918 -TGCTGaAAG - 926	ID: rs553934080 SNP ⁹²⁵ : T>C
12	RSA00973	NF-kappaB	371- GCAtATTCCC - 380	ID:rs140031290 SNP ³⁷⁴ : A>G
13	RSA01009	Ets1	745 - GAGGcAAaGA -754	ID: rs1309607581 SNP ⁷⁵² : T>G

14	RSA01233	HNF-4, and RXRalpha,	1006 -TGCCCTG -1000	ID:rs969273849 SNP ¹⁰⁰⁰ : G>T
15	RSA01258	AP-1	972 -TGACTCA -966	ID:rs1564879538 SNP ⁹⁶⁶ : A>G
16	RSA01287	MAZ/Sp1	96 -GGGGaGAGGaG - 86	ID: rs549464344 SNP ⁹⁴ : G>A

For each of the HBA1 and HBA2 genes, 23 statistically non-random motifs of known TFBSs were identified. Out of them, 21 and 16 motifs in HBA1 and HBA2 genes, respectively, contain at least one known SNP and/or indel.

For the HBB and HBD genes, 32 and 33 motifs of known TFBSs were identified. Out of them, 26 and 28 motifs in HBA1 and HBA2 genes, respectively, contain at least one known SNP and/or indel.

The effect of SNPs in TFBSs is not unambiguous. The most significant effect of SNP/indel is on HBB genes. The HBB (221) genes show higher rates of SNPs with a pathological effect, exceeding the corresponding data for the HBA1 (24), HBA2 (55), and HBD (10) genes. A similar pattern is observed for SNPs that do not have a pathological effect, and it is also noted both in the DNA coding sequences and in the 5'-UTR, 3'-UTR, and especially in the introns.

Most of the annotated SNPs/indels in both coding and non-coding regulatory regions of the genome can be considered neutral. Although introns belong to the non-coding region of the genome, the substitutions occurring in them can be associated with a number of disorders. Out of 88 SNP/indel in the promoter region of these genes, 22 were noted to have a pathological effect. Moreover, mutations in introns can make a significant contribution to the variability of the human genome and in some cases, they also have functional significance.

The presence of numerous SNPs and indels in the putative promoter elements of the 4 studied globin genes indicates that some clinical complications may be associated with mutations in non-coding regions of the genes. In this context, we assume that the results of this work can be used to assess the functional role of some SNPs and identify candidate genes for complex and monogenic diseases.

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**İnsan HBA1, HBA2, HBB və HBD genlərinin və tək nukleotid polimorfizmi
və ekspresiyası arasında mümkün əlaqələr**

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Tək nukleotid polimorfizmlərinin (TNP) funksional qiymətləndirilməsi təkamül biologiyasında, monogen və mürəkkəb xəstəliklərin genlərinin və lokuslarının xəritələşdirilməsində, genomların tənzimləyici elementlərinin təyində effektiv yanaşmalardan biridir. Xüsusilə, beta-qlobin genləri vəziyyətində, TNP-lər fərqli ağırlıq dərəcələri ilə səciyyələnən talassemiyaya səbəb ola bilər. İndiyə qədər dbSNP resurslarında (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp/>) insan genomunda müəyyən edilmiş 324 milyondan çox TNP və qısa (50 nc-dən çox olmayan) insersiyalar/delesiyalar toplanmışdır. Bu işdə globin genlərinin iki ailəsinə (alfa və beta) aid olan HBA1 və HBA2, HBB və HBD genlərinin nümunəsində insanlarda tək nukleotid polimorfizmlərinin gen ekspresiyasına təsiri ilə bağlı tədqiqatların nəticələri təqdim olunur. Bu genlərdəki 5454 (müvafiq surətdə 1245, 1181, 1777 və 1251) məlum TNP və indellərin təhlili göstərdi ki, 310 (24, 55, 221 və 10) mutasiya məlum patologiyalarla əlaqəli ola bilər və 183 (28, 22, 132 və 1) mutasiyalar isə "effektiv olmayan" (yəni simptomuz) mutasiyalardır və qalan 4961 (91%) variasiya funksional və klinik cəhətdən əhəmiyyətli deyildir. Patoloji təsirli TNP-lər arasında DNT kodlaşdırma ardıcılığında, 5'-transliyasiya olunmayan bölgələrdə (promotorlar və transkripsiya faktorları ilə bağlı potensial saytlar daxil olmaqla) və intronlarda müvafiq olaraq 262, 25 və 23 variasiya aşkar olunmuşdur. Bu nəticələr bəzi klinik ağırlaşmaların genetik səbəblərinin genlərin kodlaşdırılmayan bölgələrindəki mutasiyalar olduğuna dair məlum faktlarla uzlaşır.

Açar sözlər: *HBA1, HBA2, HBB, HBD, tək nukleotid polimorfizmi, promotor, transkripsiya faktorları ilə birləşmə saytı*